

Studies on the Influence of Some Inorganic Anions on the Extraction of Vanadium(V)-Oxine Complexes

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It is observed that vanadium(V) extracts into nitrobenzene as a mixed complex of oxine and perchlorate or chlorate or nitrate. The optimum pH range for this mixed complex formation and extraction is established for each system. Synergism is noticed in the presence of oxine and anion and this is attributed to the mixed complex formation. The formation (extraction) constants are determined. The effectiveness of the anion as synergist is found to be related to its ionic size and to the extraction constant of the mixed complex.

RECENT studies have shown that anions markedly influence the formation and extraction of several oxinate complexes^{1,2,3}. Although vanadium(V)-oxine complex is extensively investigated⁴, the effect of anions on the formation of this complex and its extraction is not reported. This paper presents the results of our investigations on these aspects.

Experimental

Apparatus: A Beckman DU-2 Spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements. The pH measurements were made on a Philips (Model PR 9405) pH meter.

Reagents: All the chemicals used were of AnalaR (BDH) grade. The solvents were distilled before use.

Results and Discussion

Borate, bromate, phosphate and sulphate are without any effect on the formation and extraction of vanadium(V)-oxine complex whatever be the solvent. However, perchlorate, nitrate and chlorate turn the characteristic magenta black colour of nitrobenzene extract of this complex green, but do not affect the magenta black colour in other, solvents.

General extraction procedure: 15.0 ml of the aqueous phase containing vanadium(V) and the anion under investigation and sufficient amount of sodium sulphate to maintain total ionic strength ($C_{SO_4^{2-}} + C_{A^-}$) constant at 2.0 M was equilibrated for two minutes with 15.0 ml of 0.1 M oxine in nitrobenzene after adjusting the pH to the desired value. The organic phase after separation was

stripped of vanadium by washing it with 1 M sulphuric acid twice. The vanadium contents in these combined washings and the original aqueous phase were determined by the vanadium(V)-oxine-alcohol method⁴. Since Beer's law was obeyed by all these three systems, the vanadium content in the organic phase could also be determined by measuring the absorbance of the nitrobenzene extract at the relevant λ_{max} after drying it over anhydrous sodium sulphate against solvent blank. The optimum pH's for perchlorate, chlorate and nitrate systems are 1.5-3.0, 1.5-2.5 and 2.5-4.0 respectively.

The ratio of vanadium to oxine in the extracting species was determined by slope analysis of $\log D$ vs $\log [HOx]_{org}$ plots in the presence of a constant excess of the corresponding anion. The ratio of vanadium to anion was determined absorptometrically by Hiskey-Meloche's method⁶ measuring the absorbance of the extracts obtained with a constant excess of oxine and varying concentrations of anion at 800 nm where the coextracting binary vanadium(V)-oxine complex species has negligible absorbance. Slope analysis technique cannot be adopted for the determination of this ratio as there is always coextraction of the binary complex. The ratio of vanadium to oxine to anion in all these cases is found to be 1 : 2 : 2.

Stability constant of vanadium(V)-oxine complex:

The extraction of vanadium with oxine into nitrobenzene in the absence of any of these anions is given by the following equilibrium:

A plot of $\log -pH$ vs $\log D_o [HOx]_{org}$ gave a straight line with slope 2 ($D_o = V(V)_{org}/V(V)_{aqueous}$). $\log K_{ex}$

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(intercept on the ordinate) is determined using the distribution coefficient of oxine (2.76) under the experimental conditions and found to be 3.8 ± 0.1 at $27.0 \pm 1^\circ$. The log K_{ex} values reported for the extraction constant in benzene and chloroform are 4.4 ± 0.1 and 4.2 ± 0.1 respectively⁶.

Determination of extraction constants of the mixed complexes : 15.0 ml of $2.7 \times 10^{-4} M$ $(VO(Ox)_2OH)$ in nitrobenzene was equilibrated with an equal volume of aqueous phase containing different concentrations of the anion under investigation at $pH \approx 1.5$ maintaining the total ionic strength constant at 2.0M with sodium sulphate. The absorbance of the extracts was found to be increasing with increasing concentrations of the anion at 640 nm. The reaction between $(VO(Ox)_2OH)$ and the anion can be shown as

(where A^- = anion under investigation)

$$K_{anion} = \frac{[VO(Ox)HOx(A)_2]_{org}}{[VO(Ox)_2OH]_{org}[A^-]^2[H^+]^2} = \frac{E_A - \epsilon_1[V]_{org}}{\epsilon_2[V]_{org} - E_A} \times \frac{1}{[H^+]^2} \times \frac{1}{[A^-]^2} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

$$= \frac{E_A - E_{min}}{E_{max} - E_A} \times \frac{1}{[H^+]^2} \times \frac{1}{[A^-]^2} \dots \dots \dots$$

Figure I : Determination of Extraction constant of the vanadium(V)-Oxine-anion mixed complexes in nitrobenzene (absorptimetric method). $[VO(Ox)_2OH]_{org} = 2.7 \times 10^{-4} M$; $pH < 1.5$

- Curve 1. Perchlorate, ($C_{ClO_4^-} = 5. \times 10^{-2} M - 5 \times 10^{-1} M$) ; 2. Thiocyanate, $C_{SCN^-} = 5 \times 10^{-2} - 7 \times 10^{-1} M$
- 3. Azide, ($C_{N_3^-} = 5 \times 10^{-2} - 7 \times 10^{-1} M$)
- 4. Chlorate, ($C_{ClO_3^-} = 5 \times 10^{-2} - 8 \times 10^{-1} M$)
- 5. Iodide, ($C_{I^-} = 3 \times 10^{-2} - 1.5 M$) ;
- 6. Fluoride, ($C_{F^-} = 4 \times 10^{-2} - 1.5 M$) ; 7. Nitrate, ($C_{NO_3^-} = 7.5 \times 10^{-2} - 2.0 M$).

where $E_A = \epsilon_1[VO(Ox)_2OH]_{org} + \epsilon_2[VO(Ox)HOx(A)_2]_{org}$.

ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are molar extinction coefficients for $VO(Ox)_2OH]_{org}$ and $[VO(Ox)HOx(A)_2]_{org}$ respectively at 640 nm. E_{min} and E_{max} are absorbances of the extracts when the concentration of the anion is zero and limiting respectively. A plot of $\log (E_A - E_{min}/E_{max} - E_A)$ against $\log[A^-] - pH$ gives straight lines (Figure I) with a slope of about 2 and the intercept of these lines on the ordinate gives the respective K_{anion} . The results are recorded in Table 1.

Figure II : Determination of extraction constant of the vanadium(V)-Oxine-anion mixed complexes in nitrobenzene. (Distribution method) $C_V = 2.7 \times 10^{-4} M$; $C_{HOx} = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} M - 1.5 \times 10^{-2} M$

$C_{anion} = 5 \times 10^{-1} M$.

- Curve 1, Perchlorate, 2. Thiocyanate, 3. Azide, 4. Chlorate, 5. Iodide, 6. Fluoride, 7. Nitrate.

TABLE-1 EXTRACTION CONSTANTS OF VANADIUM(V)-OXINE ANION MIXED COMPLEXES AT $27 \pm 1^\circ$.

Anion	log K mixed (distribution) method	log K anion distribution method	log K anion absorptimetric method
Perchlorate	8.36	4.56	4.75
Thiocyanate	8.20	4.40	4.25
Azide	7.85	4.05	4.25
Iodide	7.60	3.80	3.70
Chlorate	7.40	3.60	3.70
Fluoride	7.20	3.40	3.20
Nitrate	6.70	2.90	2.85

The extraction constants were determined from the distribution data also. The extraction of vanadium with oxine in presence of these anions can be represented by the following equilibrium

It can be shown that

$D_{\text{mixed}} = K_{\text{mixed}} [\text{HOx}]_{\text{org}}^2 [\text{H}^+] [\text{A}^-]^2$. From the plot of $\log D$ vs $2 \log [\text{HOx}]_{\text{org}} + 2 \log [\text{A}^-] - \text{pH}$ (Figure II), the values of K_{mixed} for various systems are calculated. These values ($K_{\text{mixed}} = K_{\text{anion}} \cdot K_{\text{ox}}$) are in close agreement with those obtained from absorptiometric determination. The $\log K_{\text{mixed}}$ for thiocyanate, azide and halides which form mixed complexes^{7,8,9} with vanadium(V)-oxine system are also determined now for comparison in nitrobenzene (Table 1).

Plots of E (per cent extraction) vs pH with and without the anion have shown that in all cases synergism occurred in the presence of anion at low pH ($< \text{pH } 3$). The reason for enhancement of extraction in the presence of any of these anions can now be attributed to the formation of a mixed complex $(\text{VO}(\text{Ox})\text{HOx}(\text{A})_2)$ in nitrobenzene. On the basis of the formation constants of these mixed

complexes and the percent recovery of vanadium secured with a fixed concentration of the anion, the effectiveness of these anions as synergists is found to be in the following order :

perchlorate > thiocyanate > azide > iodide \approx chlorate > fluoride > nitrate.

It is interesting to note that there is also a linear relationship between the formation constant of the mixed complex and the size of the anion (Figure III) The ionic radius of azide is not known since it is a liner molecule. Fluoride is an exception to this linear relationship.

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Figure III : Plot of $\log K_{\text{mixed}}$ against ionic radius.

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